

A STUDY OF ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG BBA STUDENT

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ABSTRACT:

Stress is usual part of life which can either aid us towards positive changes and progress or beget crucial problems in our life. Stress is feeling of emotional or physical tension in a particular situation; which varies according to individual differences. In a particular situation person faces challenges or demands and as a reaction to that situation person becomes frustrated, angry or nervous. In our day to day life we face many challenges demands; which make us feel stress some may feel stress due to career or family relation or professional life or academics or economic condition or social life and so on...

Over the past couple of decades, The warning has already gone off by the proliferation of books, research reports, popular articles and the growing number of organized workshops, Intending to teach people how to confront this phenomenon. The objective of the study is to determine the degree of academic stress among BBA students. This study involves 116 BBA students from Nashik city, Maharashtra, India. The sample was chosen using a judgmental sampling technique. The present study reveals that the BBA students are having moderate level of academic stress. Both boys and girls are stressed and there is no difference between the level of stress for boys and girls.

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INTRODUCTION:

There are various stages in the life journey of any human being. This journey starts from the infancy stage and moves from the various stages like childhood stage, adolescence stage, young adulthood stage, Middle adulthood stage, and ceases with old age stage. Adolescence is the most important time span or stage of human life.

Adolescence is the transition period in growth and development between childhood and adulthood. The transition brings dramatic, physical, sexual, psychological and social changes in development. We generally refer to adolescence as a "storm and stress." This term was first used by Stanley Hall in 1904. Hall stated that **adolescence** is a period of inevitable turmoil that takes place during the transition from childhood to adulthood. 'Storm' refers to a decreased level of self-control, and 'stress' refers to an increased level of sensitivity. Another definition of adolescence calls it as critical period i. e.

“Adolescence” is a dynamically evolving theoretical construct informed through physiologic, psychosocial, temporal and cultural lenses. This critical developmental period is conventionally understood as the years between the onset of puberty and the establishment of social independence (Steinberg, 2014). Much of adolescent’s day is occupied with educational activities. So ultimately it has effects on adolescents far broader. Adolescents may feel stressed during college time because of numerous reasons i. e. college environment, teacher’s attitude towards students, peer group relations, teacher-student relation, teaching method followed by teacher, facilities provided by school and so on. An adolescent who is going through transitional phase have to face all challenges at the same time which can be stressor for stress. Therefor it is important to understand adolescents and their academic problems.

Meaning of Adolescence:

As discussed above adolescence is a developmental stage of human’s life journey to young adulthood from childhood. Drastic Physical and psychological changes are seen at this stage. Adolescent experiences social development, emotional development & moral maturity in behavior. It is a phase of biological or physical growth in the human body. It is also a phase of Emotional and psychological development which results in change in one’s behavior and change in social relations. At this stage of adolescence adolescent develops one’s own choices, preferences, ideas, opinions and thoughts. Adolescent attain psychological maturity and they try to form their own judgments, they like to take their own decisions. This stage can also be called as the stage of emotional separation from parents or a stage of reduction in the emotional dependency on parents.

Meaning & definition of adolescent:

Adolescent is defined by the World Health Organization as the person from the age of 10 year to 19 years.

As per Cambridge Dictionary – “Adolescent is a young person who is developing into an adult.”

Academic stress:

The definition of academic stress is the anxiety and stress that comes from schooling and education. There is often a lot of pressure that comes along with pursuing a degree and one's education. It consists of studies, homework, tests, labs, reading and quizzes. Stress is about doing all the work, balancing time and finding time for extracurricular activities. Academic stress is particularly difficult for college students who have taken admission for professional courses. Teachers expect that the work will be completed in a timely manner. Students can underestimate the time required to complete reading and writing assignments, to print copies of their work.

Stress and its manifestations, such as anxiety, depression and burnout, have always been perceived as a common problem among people with different occupations. Keinan and Perlberg (1986) argue that feelings of frustration, anxiety and depression are a possible consequence of high levels of stress. Mckean et al. (2000) argue dthat stress factors alone produce no anxiety, depression or strain. Rather, the interaction between stressors and the individual's perception and response to these stressors is stressful. Environmental stress arises as a result of environmental stimuli or demands apprehended by an

individual beyond his or her capacity to manage them (Shirom, 1986).

Academic stress among students have long been researched on, and researchers have identified stressors as too many assignments, competitions with other students, failures and poor relationships with other students or lecturers (Fairbrother& Warn, 2003). Academic stressors include the student's perception of the extensive knowledge base required and the perception of an inadequate time to develop it (Carveth et al, 1996) The pressure to perform well in the examination or test and time allocated makes academic environment very stressful (Erkutlu&Chafra, 2006). This is likely to affect the social relations both within the institution and outside which affects the individual person's life in terms of commitment to achieving the goals (Fairbrother& Warn, 2003). As per the study conducted by National Institute of Mental Health and Neuroscience (NIMHANS) about the growing number of suicides in India among school and college going students, 11 percent of college students and 7 to 8 percent of high school students have attempted suicide

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

1. Sibnath Deb, EsbenStrodl and Jiandong Sun (2012). Academic-related stress among private secondary school students in India. The purpose of this study is to examine the prevalence of academic stress and exam anxiety among private secondary school students in India as well as the associations with socio-economic and study-related factors. Participants were 400 adolescent students (52 percent male) from five private secondary schools in Kolkata who were studying in grades 10 and 12. Participants were selected using a multi-stage sampling technique and were assessed using a study-specific questionnaire. Findings revealed that 35 and 37 percent reported high or very high levels of academic stress and exam anxiety respectively. All students reported high levels of academic stress, but those who had lower grades reported higher levels of stress than those with higher grades. Students who engaged in extra-curricula activities were more likely to report exam anxiety than those who did not engage in extra-curricula activities.
2. Marwan Zaid Bataineh (2013). Academic stress among undergraduate students: the case of education faculty at King Saud University. This study investigated the academic stressors experienced by the students at university. A total sample of 232 subjects participated in this study were obtained from faculty of education at KSU. Data were collected through self- administered questionnaire which was randomly distributed to the students during lecture time. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The result showed that academic overloads, course awkward, inadequate time to study, workload every semester, exams awkward, low motivation, and high family expectations were drive moderately stress among students. It was also found that fear of failure is the major source of stress among undergraduate students. Moreover, the study found that there were positive correlation between religiosity sources and academic stress ($r= .300^{**}$, $p=.00$). Lastly, the study found that there were no significant differences in academic stress among students with different, level of study and specializations.

3. Rajasekar (2013). Impact of academic stress among the management students of AMET university – An analysis. The study examined the impact of academic stress among the management students. Stress management encompasses techniques to equip a person with effective coping mechanisms for dealing with psychological stress. Students have different expectations, goals and values that they want to fulfill, which is only possible if they are integrated with that of the institution. The objective of the study is to find out the present level of stress, sources of stress and stress management techniques that would be useful for management students. The study takes into account various criteria like physical, psychological, individual, demographical and environmental factors of stress among the management students. The sample comprises of 100 students of AMET Business School, AMET University in Chennai. Data was collected through structured questionnaire by using convenient sampling method.
4. Yikealo, D. , Yemane, B. and Karvinen, I. (2018) The Level of Academic and Environmental Stress among College Students: A Case in the College of Education. In this research, the level of academic and environmental stress at the College of Education (CoE) of the IET was discovered intensively. It was studied in relation to the cumulative weighted average of students and their gender. The principal educational and environmental factors that contribute to increased stress among college students were of great interest to the study. In addition, the survey on stress management strategies practiced by college students was a major concern. To obtain a reliable data, a total of 107 students of 2nd, 3rd, and 4th year of the College of Education were randomly and conveniently selected to fill the self-developed questionnaire and in the focus group discussion. The data were analyzed with the help of descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The data computation process was assisted by a Software Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The results of the study indicate that the majority of College of Education students experience moderate levels of academic and environmental stress. The gender and cumulative grade point average of the students showed no statistically significant differences. However, it was only found that the CGPA had a slight statistically significant relationship to the level of environmental stress. The majority of students expressed their opinions using a variety of positive stress management strategies.

NEED OF THE STUDY:

In today's highly competitive world, students face various academic challenges, including exam stress, lack of interest in attending classes and inability to understand the subject. Academic stress is the feeling of anxiety or apprehension over one's performance in the academic activities. It may lead to students being incapable of performing to the best of their abilities in exams.

At college there is a range of academic pressure feel, derived from a need for perfection, worry over grades, parental pressure, competition, career, tough class load. The nervous breakdowns, panic attacks, burnouts, and depression are also apparent in many younger students. The same situation is not

always stressful for all people, and all people do not undergo the same feelings or off-putting thoughts when stressed.

Students have been seen as the future pillars that take on the responsibility of taking our country to the next stage, they should be better. To find out, the researcher decided to study academic stress among college students.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A study of Academic stress among BBA students.”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To find out the level of academic stress among BBA students in Nashik city.
2. To find out whether there is significant difference between academic stress level of girls and boys of BBA students.

HYPOTHESIS:

1. BBA students of Nashik city have academic stress.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female students of BBA with respect to academic stress.

METHODS:

Researcher has applied normative survey method for present study. The normative study method studies, describes and interprets what exist at present.

SAMPLE:

The present study consists 116 BBA students from Nashik city. To select the sample judgmental sampling technique is used.

TOOLS:

Academic Stress of the subjects was assessed by applying Academic Stress Scale developed by P.B. Sreenivas and B.S. Kumar (1999), which consists of 40 items.

40 items are divided into five components.

1. Personal inadequacy
2. Fear of failure
3. Interpersonal difficulties with teachers
4. Teacher - Pupil relationship / Teaching methods
5. Inadequate study facilities

Among 40 statements, eight are related to each component. Each statement has five options varying from the response of "No Stress" to "Extreme Stress" with regard to the degree of stress. So the scoring to the response given by the students should be like the following-

Response	Score
No stress	0
Slight Stress	1
Moderate Stress	2
High Stress	3
Extreme Stress	4

Therefore 160 (4x40) is the maximum possible score and the highest score on each factor would be 32. Each factor has equal number of items. High score indicates high academic stress. The reliability of the instrument was established by test - retest method and it is 0.84

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED:

For the analysis of the data, the following statistical techniques have been used.

- Descriptive analysis (Mean & S.D)
- Differential analysis (t^o test)

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis 1: BBA students have academic stress.

TABLE 1

Variable	Sample	N	No stress	Slight Stress	Moderate stress	High stress	Extreme stress
Academic stress	BBA students	116	1	36	56	20	3

In Table no.1 level of Academic stress is shown. While considering academic stress level of all BBA students it is found that 48% students have moderate stress, 31% students have slight stress, 17% students have High stress, 3% students have extreme stress and only 1% student have no stress. The distribution of level of academic stress in percentage is shown below in pie chart.

TABLE - 2

**SHOWING THE MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF ACADEMIC STRESS SCORES
OF BBA STUDENTS**

Variable	Sample	N	M	S. D.	t- value	Significant at 0.05 level
Academic Stress	Male	58	57.44	31.03	0.410	Not significant
	Female	58	56.20	27.28		

1. In table no. 2 t value is calculated of academic stress score of male and female students of BBA. No significant difference is found in academic stress score of male and female students of BBA students. It means the null hypothesis is accepted i. e. There is no significant difference between male and female students of BBA with respect to academic stress.

FINDINGS:

1. BBA students from Nashik city have academic stress.
2. Overall 48% students have moderate, 31% students have slight, 17% students have high and only 1% student has noacademic stress.
3. 33% girls and 29% boys have slight academic stress, 55% girls and 44% boys have moderate academic stress, 14% girls and 20% boys have high stress and only boys (5%) have extreme academic stress.
4. Overall there is no significant difference between academic stress level of girls and boys but it is notable that only boys have extreme academic stress.

CONCLUSION:

The present study reveals that the BBA students from Nashik city have academic stress. There is no significant difference between the degree of academic stress of boys and girls. Only boys have extreme academic stress may be its cause is BBA is professional course, which expect professionalism along with academics than general course like commerce arts...

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